

Internet Addiction and the Postpartum Depression in Pandemic

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Abstract: *The addiction on internet is spread on the hole globe and include all the age and social gourps. Postpartum depression is caused as also accelerated and magnified in many cases in situations of isolation (social, medical, living, professional). The own perception about isolation varies from person to person and the consequences are depending on the degree of frustration which some deprivation are inducing it. The mother has the sensation of unjustice of the destiny, that she deserves on a certain plan something more and this dissatisfaction will lead her to be to upset, worried, undecided, anxious and asbamed, helplessness and finally depressed. The spectrum of the postpartum depression is extended up to demisive behavior (abandonment of the job, career, extended family, friends and even the husband) in many cases because of the fear not to be accepted or not to upset the others. The difficulties encountered bu the investigators and the therapists it consists precisely in the fact that it is needed to define correct and concrete this subjective experiences and also to measure them and to correlate them with the actions and the evaluated consequences of the patients actions. The bet with destiny which the woman made it many times, she tries in the moment of depression that she has lost, and just her baby can become the existential motivation to go further and this happens often to mothers with a psychovulnerabilizant family hystory and there are situations in which this assumption seems to look very bad for the women and so the women tries to argue and to justify some of her behaviors. This hard journey form denial to awareness and after that assumption and reconciliation can be traversed with specialised help focused focused on the mother who wants to manage her past in a new setting.*

Keywords: *addiction, internet, pandemic, postpartum depression.*

How to cite: Stan, B.-C., Elkan, E.-M., Papuc, A.-M., Voinescu, D.C., & Ciubara, A. (2022). Internet Addiction and the Postpartum Depression in Pandemic. *BRAIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 13(1), 239-245. <https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/13.1/281>

Introduction

The uncertainty, the shortages, the daily variation of social rules, of the working rules and the permanently appearance of events that are disturbing the free time can lead to the voluntary or involuntary readjustment of the reality which becomes fragmented (Huidu, 2018; Neculau et al., 2018; Rodideal, 2019; Sandu & Nistor, 2020) for the mother which must respond to the challenge of new family roles. The mother is the person from which the others are requiring to be the anchor and the shore in the pandemic and her duty is to bring the peace and happiness in the family, and the expectations from her are that she to become a balanced and quiet person as also a prudent, calm and confident person (Baroiu et al., 2021; Luca, Baroiu et al., 2020). There are existing divergent opinions about the utilisation of the internet, because the internet permits connections which in other situations would not be possible, between peoples with similar ideas and conceptions about life but which in their social microgroup are not finding peoples with the same ideas, but on the other hand it is lost the valuable time for the interactions face to face with other peoples.

The fathers can have also postpartum depression in a percentage of 4-25%, the fathers are expressing more the anger and fear rather their sadness (Melrose, 2010; Radulescu 2020). Sometimes the parents of a child can confront with the onset of a chronic disease of their child against which they feel powerless. The psychologic therapy addresses to the mothers which use the internet and is cognitiv-behavioral and this therapy will combat the maladaptive behaviors and will bring the correction of some wrong beliefs and convictions and the interpersonal psychotherapy. The women avoid to seek help because they have fear to be badged because of this diagnostic. The therapy will help the women to process their visions with negative impact about what maternity is and the role as a mother it seems to overwhelm them. In fact a role negotiation is made as also the loss processing and the confrontation which the mother learns to do with her proper person and her proper ambivalence (Fonseca, 2018). The patients with postpartum depression have a modification of the psychic tonus, dysphoria and have emotional oscillations, sleep disorders going to insomnia, confusing states of different intensities and anxiety which can go up to panic attacks, feelings of guilt toward the child and toward the partner and the anxiety not to cope with the familial and social roles. There are also suicidal thoughts in this patients, and 50% of this women do not address to a psychiatrist to seek help (Leturneau, et al., 2007; Sakakihara, 2019).

Objectives

We want to show the unseen face of the suffering of the mother who takes refuge on the internet, generated by the personal history, by her anxieties, by taboos, inadequate support, perturbed social and family roles. The support of this distressed women protects the child and the whole family.

Results

The mothers no longer having the support of the extended family that often disappears due to the pandemic (protection of grandparents of the child which can no longer come in contact with the family because of the danger to take the virus), the mother will seek help in the virtual space. The mother will try to get information from internet parent groups to learn how to raise her child better to keep him out of the hospital (where she and her child can get infections and the hospital is the place where she will get a PCR testing and she is not sure if the consequence will not be the isolation of their and her family). The pandemic is complicating the contact with relatives and friends together with the problems at the job of both the father and mother can lead to alienation and so the mother will lose the support from the person she needed most, her husband. The harsh reality she will try to counteract, by looking for words of wit on the internet to strengthen her, to go through the pandemic and overcome the difficulties of her child's newborn age. Because of the excessive utilisation of the phone, internet, TV she will neglect involuntarily her child and she will lose the interaction which can put her in a good light before her family and the self-worth in one's own eyes. If there appear observations and critics in the family, the feelings of guilt of the mother will grow and the greatest guilt she will have thinking that she has born a child in hard times and she will feel guilt also toward the husband because she cannot be a good mother and a good wife. The mother will take distance toward the colleagues and friends because she will try to put a mask over her suffering and she will try to communicate with other people on internet to comfort her. The women which use the internet to ask about information about birth and child's education are 66-75%. There are risk factors on which it is very hard to act, such as life history, the previous depressive episodes that load it with an even higher risk, the environment of origin. Many women will avoid to seek help because the postpartum depression is a corollary and other problems which the woman cannot manage and in this way fear may arise about the exposure to the authorities (Filip Drozd, 2015). The excessive utilisation of the internet from mothers and the disruption of the sleep

program of the child and that's why children become confused and angry and are after that exposed to the psychical and physical abuse from the mothers. The internet is used by some persons to counterbalance the feelings of guilt and helplessness because the own poor management of their lives and the way they are perceived by the society (Sakakihara, 2019). Other therapies which can rebalance the women with postpartum depression compared to conventional ones and international accepted according to the actual guidelines are the white light of 10.000 lux up to 30 minutes per day. The postpartum depression intervenes when the child it still depends on the quality of the interactions with the adults. The children of depressive mothers can develop retardation in mental aquisition (verbal, motor) as also retardation in the social interactions (Dennis et al., 2019).The figure 1 shows how the facts can escalate from tensions and depression to violence.

Figure 1. The cicle of violence after Aya Sakakihara (2019)

So where? The role of the multidiciplinary team is to intervene in this situation of balance which can evolve to real crisis, and the role of the team is to offer to the mother safe and secure alternatives for a dialogue with meaningful sense and direction with the purpose to help her to slide elegantly through the hardships of dayly life, and so the mother can feel she is part of the social life and that she is still a women which is appreciated, understood and that she is a secure base of atachment for her child. We want to offer a model of intervention for the mothers in difficulty in the

pandemic and we want to prevent the development of major depressive episodes in the postpartum period which can have as a consequence the endangering the harmonious development of the child and the damage of the mental health of the mother on long term.

Discussions

The Program ADI-ADDS-W (Internet Adiction and Depressions In Women) designed by our team is a new instrument to combat the addiction on internet for the depressed women:

- the mothers will complete a questionnaire for the inclusion in the study as also they will make (if they wish) a voice registration of their needs, because written answers can differ from the information given by voice registration and we will have more spontaneous information production

- the internet can become a good tool to combat even the addiction on internet and the mothers postpartum depression- because we can generate working groups on internet and Whatsup –therapeutic groups for mothers or even individual therapy with permanently renewed audiovisual media with the purpose to interact with the beneficiaries (Grigoras & Ciubara, 2021; Luca, Burlea et al., 2020; Pandeale et al., 2021).

- The therapist can accompany the mother in the precious time spent with her child

- counselling from the neonatologist who is part of the team

- creating a neurologist-neonatologist-psychologist trinomial to discuss each case

Conclusions

Indifferent of what kind of protocol is used for the rehabilitation of the mother with different addictions as also the addiction to the inadequate use of the internet, the basic principles are the family support, the social and educational insertion and the interdisciplinary vision of the specialists with the maintainance in the pandemic of a secure remote so that the mothers can feel that every moment they are understanding, security and support.

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